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Executive Summary

SPATRA aims at increasing the use of satellite data in land transport by developing two new downstream applications for monitoring and management of rail and road transport and demonstrating them in operational environment. Satellite data will be used in combination with assisted in-situ data to develop two innovative applications for smart transport and logistics, to solve problems of principal modes of land transport, road and rail: road traffic congestions and negative impact of extreme temperatures on railway infrastructure.

SPATRA will establish two live pilot use cases for railway and road transportation that will be demonstrated in real-world environments, engaging all relevant stakeholders to ensure wide take-up, sustainable development, expansion, and exploitation of the project's results. Validation of the new solutions and interfaces ready for integration with existing road logistics system and management, as well as with rail infrastructure management, will lead to improved products, processes or services which are based on the EU space technologies (Copernicus, EGNSS as enabler) - that are capable of generating a marketable solution for the local market.

This deliverable document, (D1.1), reports the activities, effort and work undertaken in Work Package 1 (WP1-Project management) of the SPATRA project, focused on the Project Management Plan (PMP). The aim of the PMP is to present the plan for efficient and effective project management. This version, v2, of deliverable D1.1 reflects the changes in the project Consortium and in the PMP introduced by inclusion of a new beneficiary, DUTH, as approved by the GA Amendment closed on 17th October 2024.

List of abbreviations, acronyms and definitions

Abbreviation / Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
EGNSS	European Global Navigation Satellite System
EO	Earth Observation
GA	Grant Agreement
GEAS	General Assembly
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IM	Innovation Manager
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LST	Land Surface Temperature
PMP	Project Management Plan
SB	Stakeholder Board
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SPATRA	SPace-based Applications for TRAnsport monitoring and management
S&T	Scientific & Technical Coordination
TL	Task Leader
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

SPATRA will use satellite data assisted by in-situ data to develop two innovative applications for smart transport and logistics, to solve problems of principal modes of land transport, road and rail:

- SPATRA will provide benefits of **satellite-based logistics and road traffic flow monitoring** by reducing congestion and improving the flow of goods and people.
- A novel **space-based service predicting the risk of rail buckling** based on a downstream application for estimation of the rail temperature will be developed to support prevention of train derailments induced by track buckling.

The work plan of SPATRA is organized in five highly interacting, incremental, and iterative work packages (WPs), where WP1 performs the administrative and financial management of the project and coordinates the Research & Development activities of the different WPs with the help of the WP leaders.

This deliverable D1.1 represent the first deliverable of WP1, namely, the Project Management Plan (PMP), which outlines how the project will be executed. It provides a roadmap for managing project activities. This deliverable D1.1 will be followed with two more deliverables of WP1, D1.2- Risk management and project quality plan and D1.3- Data Management Plan (DMP). All three deliverables will report on project work and effort to achieve WP1 goals, specifically:

- O1.1: Manage the project through administrative, financial and innovation coordination.
- O1.2: Ensure the submission of project deliverables and achievement of project results on time and ensure effective communications within the consortium and with the EC/EUSPA.
- O1.3: Develop project DMP and manage regulatory requirements.

The PMP will be a live document that will be revised as the project progresses to accommodate eventual changes.

This version, v2, deliverable D1.1 of (PMP) reflects the changes in the project Consortium and Project Management Plan introduced by inclusion of new beneficiary, DUTH, as approved by the GA Amendment closed on 17th October 2024.

The D1.1 document is prepared using the SPATRA project template for project deliverables that has been produced to introduce use of a standard format including defined styles, page layout and content structure. This template has been prepared by the Project Management Team and it is available on the project share point under “General Documents-Templates”. The document is organized as follows. Chapter 2 provides an overview of the project, including its objectives, scope, and expected outcomes. Project organization is given in Chapter 3. This Chapter describes the organizational structure of the project, including the project team, roles, responsibilities, and reporting lines. Work breakdown structure is given in Chapter 4. This Chapter gives also the list of project deliverables, specific outputs or reports that will be submitted during the project, as well as the list of milestones, which are the control points that mark significant achievements that allow the project to move forward.

2. Project objectives overview

SPATRA aims at increasing the use of satellite data in land transport by developing two demonstrators in new downstream applications for monitoring and management of rail and road transport.

The starting point for the road pilot development is that by combining the positioning, navigation, and timing with Earth Observation (EO) services through the use of EGNSS and Copernicus, the real-time monitoring of road traffic flow and prediction of logistics networks, contributing to the optimization of transport routes and reduction of carbon emissions, could be achieved. While acknowledging the limitations of real-time detection, the project will integrate space assets with other open data sources such as weather patterns to develop more sophisticated classifiers that can predict congestion with higher accuracy. By providing prediction information on traffic flows and congestion based on Sentinel-2, assisted with EGNSS-based drones and location trackers, assisted with open data, SPATRA will be capable to detect and predict the traffic flow.

The starting point for the rail pilot is the assumption that using satellite data such as Sentinel-3 and Landsat might enable services for identifying the railway areas that are most exposed to severe impacts resulted from weather phenomena. Satellite-based services can make the railway operation more resilient against severe weather events such as extreme heat, by creating risk analytics from satellite data and translating them into actionable insights. In particular, satellite-based services for future readiness and early warning of extreme heat induced damages in specific rail tracks zones could be a basis for identification of the areas where railway network infrastructures are most exposed to such events and for targeted intervention to prevent and mitigate the outage risks.

2.1 Objectives and ambitions

The overall objective of SPATRA is broken down into four specific objectives that are listed in the following Table along with the expected results and relevance to the Work Programme related to the topic HORIZON-EUSPA-2022-SPACE-02-56 — Designing space-based downstream applications with international partners.

Objective 1: Develop innovative downstream applications for road traffic monitoring and management by combining positioning navigation and timing with Earth Observation (EO) services through the use of EGNSS and Copernicus. (*Addressed by WP2, WP3*)

Results:

- R1.1 – Algorithm for truck detection from Sentinel-2 images;
- R1.2 – Road-infrastructure detection algorithm based on the Open maps;
- R1.3 – Open-source dataset for truck detection from Sentinel-2;
- R1.4 – Image vision algorithm for truck detection for drone camera;
- R1.5 – Positioning algorithm based on EGNSS interface for drones and trucks;
- R1.6 – Real-time dashboards: info on deviations compared to the initial plans, showing alerts and recommendations to take action, facilitating the decision-making process.

Pertinence to the Work Programme. The combined use of EGNSS and Copernicus will lead to innovative SPATRA space-based downstream application for road transport. During the project lifetime, SPATRA space-based application will be shared with an end-user from international partner country, NELT logistic operator, and will so introduce EU-space based solutions into logistic community presenting potential of generating a marketable solution for the local market.

Objective 2: Develop innovative downstream service for monitoring and prediction of extreme temperatures impact to railways and early warnings using Copernicus data. (*Addressed by WP2, WP3*)

Results:

- R2.1 – Rail environment temperature profile map based on satellite data;
- R2.2 – Algorithm for estimation of rail temperature in the railway network based on satellite data and machine learning;
- R2.3 – Algorithm for assessment of rail buckling risks in the rail network and early warnings.

Pertinence to the Work Programme. Through the collaboration with partners from the international partner country, Serbia, a novel service will be jointly developed using Copernicus data that will address local and global negative impact of extreme temperatures to railway infrastructure. During the project lifetime, SPATRA space-based application will be shared with a public end-user, Serbian Railway Infrastructure, and will so introduce EU-space based solutions into railway community presenting potential of generating a marketable solution. Having non-EU partners, SPATRA will contribute to the ever-growing use of Copernicus services across the Europe's regions.

Objective 3: Evaluate developed algorithms and compatible techniques and technology in laboratory and carry out demonstration activities in real-world rail and road environment, comprising all relevant stakeholders to ensure wide take-up, sustainable development, expansion, and exploitation of the project's results. (*Addressed by WP4*)

Results:

- R3.1 – Validation of the project's infrastructure with potential end users;
- R3.2 – Pilots established to test space technology-based monitoring technology and additional devices;
- R3.3 – Demonstration of the technologies at relevant pilot scale in two domains;
- R3.4 – Evaluation of results and extract lessons learned from monitoring and prediction of the downstream applications.

Pertinence to the Work Programme. Using the EU space-based technologies, SPATRA will develop innovative solutions that will be validated in relevant environment in international partner country demonstrating so the advantages and differentiators of EU space-based solutions and services and making it an attractive option for public authorities, private industries and private investors in Europe and elsewhere. Validation activities will include integration of local in-situ systems to enhance the quality of data and service products.

Objective 4: Promote the uptake of EU space technologies with outreach campaigns and to enable non-EU countries to benefit from their advanced features and build capacity and awareness rising around Galileo, EGNOS and Copernicus applications. (*Addressed by WP5*)

Results:

R4.1 – Dissemination, exploitation and communications plans, agreed with all partners;

R4.2 – 10 dialogues, engaging at least 10 participants per stakeholder;

R4.3 – An analysis of scale-up and replication in different countries and domains;

R4.4 – Exploitation plan with business model with IPR;

R4.5 – Liaison with EU projects and ecosystems, and communities;

R4.6 – Working groups on standardisation.

Pertinence to the Work Programme. SPATRA Consortium includes two non-EU partner countries that have signed a Copernicus Cooperation Agreement, Serbia and Ukraine, contributing so to building capacity and awareness raising, around EGNSS and Copernicus based applications and solutions. SPATRA partners will also reach out other international partners through the set dissemination and communication activities.

3. Project management and organisation

Project management defines the project’s organizational structures and partners’ roles and responsibilities, decision making procedures and communication tools and resources to be used for promoting the collaboration among project partners. It also gives a detailed preview of monitoring and reporting procedures for realized activities and incurred expenditure, necessary for preparation and validation of project’s deliverables.

The overall project management of SPATRA will comply with the following two principles: (1) Principle of creating an integrated project structure incorporating technical, scientific and partner coordination as well as issues of commonplace business operation, based on the project management methodology, successfully applied in pervious collaborative projects, and supported with state-of-the-art management instruments; (2) Principle of achieving agreement among all partners in a collaborative endeavour while safeguarding intellectual properties of all partners.

The responsibilities and tasks of the Coordinator and the Work Package Leaders and different decision-making bodies are described in detail in separate sections below.

3.1 Consortium

SPATRA Consortium encompasses all relevant actors who are necessary to reach the project objectives. It consists of six partners from five European countries, including two associated non-EU countries that have signed a Copernicus Cooperation Agreement, Serbia and Ukraine. In spite of relatively small size of the Consortium, the SPATRA Consortium brings together a unique combination of research, technology, potential end users, demonstration, evaluation, innovation, business skills and expertise necessary to achieve its goals. The partners possess excellence in their respective field of competence, thus providing complementary know-how for the successful completion of the project. An overview table of SPATRA partners and their expertise, role in the project, is given below.

Table 1. SPATRA Consortium

Partner	Role in the project
 (OHBDS) OHB Digital Services, Germany	Project Coordinator, leader of WP 1 – Project management and coordination, Leader of WP3, and the main responsible partner for EO-based rail service prototype integration
 (UNI) University of Niš, Serbia Faculty of Mechanical Engineering	Leader of WP 4 – Validation: Use-cases, Main responsible partner for development of the algorithm for assessment of rail track buckling risk in Task 3.7, Provider of the direct contact to Serbian Railway Infrastructure, end-user of the rail pilot prototype

<p>(ZENE) Zentrix lab, Estonia</p>	<p>Leader of WP2 - Requirements and specifications, Main responsible partner for development of the satellite-based components of the road pilot, Copernicus Sentinel-2 truck detection and in-truck EGNSS trackers.</p>
<p>(ZENRS) Privredno drustvo Zentrix Lab, Serbia (affiliated partner to ZENE)</p>	<p>Innovation Manager, Leader of all tasks of WP5 - Dissemination, communication and exploitation</p>
<p>(NELT) NELT, Serbia</p>	<p>Leader of the work on specification of the use cases for testing and validation methodology, The end-user partner for the road pilot prototype</p>
<p>(Twist) Twist Robotics, Ukraine</p>	<p>Contributor to development of Machine learning / Image vision for UAVs in Task 3.3</p>
<p>(DUTH) Democritus University of Thrace, Greece</p>	<p>Leader of the UAV (drone)-related work in road work stream; Leader of Tasks T3.3 and T4.1</p>

In summary, there are four industrial partners in SPATRA Consortium, OHB-DS, ZEN, ZENRS and Twist, out of which three are SMEs (ZEN, ZENRS and Twist). Besides their business competence, industrial partners will be involved in SPATRA through their Research & Innovation departments. The Research & Innovation activities will be strongly supported by the Scientific Organisation (University) UNI and DUTH. UNI will also be the main partner to ensure the involvement of end-user for the rail pilot, Serbian Railway Infrastructure, and they will strongly

cooperate on rail use case with OHB-DS. NELT will be the end-user partner for the road pilot who will closely cooperate on this use case with ZENE, DUTH and Twist. Besides the leading Research & Innovation role for the rail pilot, OHB-DS will be the project coordinator and will leverage previous significant experience in coordinating the collaborative projects into coordination and management of SPATRA.

3.2 Project management structure

The SPATRA project management structure was planned during the preparation of the project proposal and was adopted upon the SPATRA internal project Kick-off meeting (online, 12th January 2024). Figure 1 presents the project management structure in SPATRA. It is designed to meet the challenges involved in a project of this size and nature, and in particular of EUSPA (as the granting authority), the contributing industrial and scientific partners, as well as the research and innovation base of Europe.

Figure 1. SPATRA project management structure

Project Coordinator

The overall project coordination will be the responsibility of Dr.-Ing. Danijela Ristić-Durrant, OHB Digital Services (OHB-DS). The Coordinator will be the official link between the Consortium and EUSPA. She is also the direct supervisor of the Project Manager, a member of the OHB-DS team, who will be appointed to assist the project coordinator and will act as the project Scientific & Technical Coordinator. The Coordinator will also be supported in her role by the Innovation Manager and the project General Assembly (GEAS).

The main management activities of the Scientific & Technical Coordinator are:

- co-ordination of scientific and technical progress,

- review and assessment of technical reports and deliverables against objectives using objectively verifiable project indicators and the main project milestones,
- resolution of problems and management of risks; Risk management procedures will be detailed in D1.2.
- reporting to the Project Coordinator and adopting the quality procedures of SPATRA; Quality procedures will be detailed in D1.2.

The main responsibilities of the Coordinator are:

- management of all contacts with the EUSPA; Distribution of EUSPA-funds to partners and Management of the common fund;
- preparation and timely submission to the EUSPA of consolidated technical and financial reports;
- communication of any documents and information connected with the project between the concerned partners,
- monitoring of the partners' use of resources

Work Package Leaders

The WP Leaders play a key role for the success of the SPATRA project and, therefore, scientists and high level industrial managers with extensive research and project management experience have been chosen as coordinators for the research and technology development focused on WPs 2-4, the horizontal activities of WP 5 (Dissemination and Exploitation) and WP 1 (Management and Coordination) as follows:

WP1 – Project Management Leader (also Scientific & Technical Coordinator): Alina Klapper (OHB-DS)

WP2 – Requirements and specifications: Nenad Gligoric (ZENE)

WP3 – Development of SPATRA algorithms and technology: Alina Klapper (OHB-DS)

WP4 – Validation: Use-cases: Milan Banic (UNI)

WP5 – Dissemination, communication and exploitation: Jelena Vasic (ZENRS)

The main responsibilities of the Work Package Leaders are:

- to provide the scientific lead and settle scientific dispute arising within the WP;
- to maintain overall progress of the WP against milestones and deliverables;
- to prepare and timely submit consolidated technical WP reports to the Scientific & Technical Coordinator;
- to transfer any other documents, information and deliverables connected with the WP to the Scientific & Technical Coordinator;
- to organise internal reviews of progress (WP meetings; as video conferences or personal meetings when appropriate) with task leaders; WP meetings will be organised at least

monthly and more frequently, bi-weekly or weekly, if dynamics of the project progress demands.

- to administrate and prepare minutes and provision of the chairperson of the WP meetings, and to follow up its decisions.

Task Leaders (TLs)

A Task Leader will be appointed by the partner leading the task. Distribution of Tasks' leaderships is as follows:

Table 2. Distribution of tasks' leaderships and partners tasks' contribution roles

Task	Leader	Contributors/Roles
1.1 – Project coordination	OHB-DS	ALL partners have dedicated efforts in this task to assure the support to the coordinator and to provide necessary inputs for all management tasks, and periodic reports to be submitted to EC/EUSPA.
1.2 – Scientific & Technical Coordination	OHB-DS	ALL partners have dedicated efforts in this task to assure the support to S&T coordinator and to provide necessary inputs for technical reports and deliverables.
1.3 - Innovation Management	ZENRS	ALL partners have dedicated efforts in this task to assure the support to Innovation Manager, and to regularly report on own innovation activities.
1.4 - Elaborate the project's DMP, ethics and regulatory strategy	OHB-DS	ALL partners have dedicated efforts in this task to assure the support to Task Leader in elaboration of the project's DMP, ethics and regulatory strategy. Also, ALL partners will be involved in activities regarding Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection.
2.1 - Define SPATRA functional and non-functional requirements	OHB-DS	ALL partners have dedicated efforts in this task to assure participations in stakeholder consultations that will support definition of requirements for both project workstreams. OHB-DS and UNI will be involved in the activities of rail workstream. ZENE, ZENRS, NELT and Twist will be involved in the activities of road workstream.
2.2 - Develop use-case specification	ZENE	ALL partners have dedicated efforts in this task to assure own contributions in specification of use-cases. OHB-DS and UNI will be involved in the specifications of rail use-case. ZENE, ZENRS, NELT and Twist will be involved in the specifications of rail use-case.
2.3 - Devise a component specification and integration roadmap	UNI	ZENE, NELT and Twist will be involved in the specifications of the components of the road pilot. OHB-DS and UNI will be involved in the specifications of the components of the rail pilot.
3.1 Data collection, harmonisation, storage, and interoperability API	OHB-DS	UNI, ZENE, DUTH and Twist will support Task Leader, OHB-DS, in establishing of a data collection, harmonisation, storage, and interoperability framework to support the other tasks in the project.

3.2 Copernicus Sentinel-2 truck detection	ZENRS	ZENRS is the main responsible partner for development of the Sentinel-2 based algorithm for truck detection. NELT will support ZENRS by providing needed end-user inputs/perspective. Twist will be involved to assure that all needed inputs for Task 3.3 are provided as outcomes of this Task 3.2.
3.3 Machine learning / Image vision for Drone	DUTH	DUTH, as a new beneficiary who joined the consortium upon approved Amendment on 17 th October 2024, took over the leadership of a large proportion of the Tasks that were originally assigned to partner Twist. DUTH will lead task 3.3, and it will be the main responsible for the EGNSS Location Positioning based on EGNSS-based drone module to accurately determine the location of the drone during monitoring operations. Twist will contribute to machine learning (ML)-based image processing algorithm that can detect and classify objects in the drone images by generation of dataset for development of ML algorithm and in validation of developed ML algorithm.. ZENE and ZENRS will be involved to assure that the inputs from related tasks 3.2 and 3.4 are provided for 3.1, as well as to assure that the task 3.3 outputs are provided in for needed for integration into road pilot.
3.4 In-truck EGNSS trackers	ZENE	ZENE is the main responsible for developing the HW as needed for road pilot. NELT will support ZENE by providing needed end-user inputs/perspective and by enabling vehicles for testing of developed HW.
3.5 Rail environment temperature profile based on satellite data	OHB-DS	OHB-DS is the main responsible partner for development and implementation of high-resolution LST product for rail environment temperature profile. UNI will be involved to assure that outcomes of this Task 3.5 fulfill the requirements of Task 3.7.
3.6 Rail track temperature prediction model	OHB-DS	OHB-DS is the main responsible partner for development of machine learning-based algorithm for rail track temperature prediction based on the rail environment temperature profile developed in Task 3.5. UNI will be involved to assure that outcomes of this Task 3.6 fulfill the requirements for Task 3.7.
3.7 Algorithm for assessment of rail track buckling risk	UNI	UNI is the main responsible partner for development of a decision making algorithm for assessment of rail track buckling risk due to extreme temperatures. The algorithm will be developed according to specifications that will be defined in cooperation with Serbian Railway Infrastructure. OHB-DS will be involved to assure that the outputs of Tasks 3.5 and 3.6 are provided correctly, as needed for development of this Task 3.7.
3.8. Implementation of space-based service for monitoring of rail temperature and early	OHB-DS	OHB-DS is the main responsible for implementation of an integrated Earth Observation (EO) and spatial data platform cloud solution for rail pilot. UNI will be involved to assure proper integration of the component developed in Task 3.7.

warnings		
3.9 GUI Dashboard	OHB-DS	OHB-DS will be the main responsible partner for development of a single-access user-oriented GUI for both use cases, road and rail. UNI will be involved to support developing interface to rail pilot components. ZENE and ZENRS will be involved to support developing interface to road pilot components. NELT will be involved to provide necessary user perspective.
4.1 - Specification of the use cases for testing and validation methodology	NELT	ALL partners will be involved in specification of SPATRA scenarios for testing the developed solutions for both pilots. NELT, ZENE, ZENRS, DUTH and Twist will be involved in specifications of validation scenario for road pilot. OHB-DS and UNI will be involved in specifications of validation scenario for rail pilot.
4.2 - Configure and establish SPATRA pilots	UNI	OHB-DS and UNI will be involved in configuration process to establish SPATRA rail pilot. ZENE, ZENRS, NELT, DUTH and Twist will be involved in configuration process to establish SPATRA road pilot.
4.3 - Integration and validation of modules	ZENE	DUTH, Twist, ZENRS and NELT will be involved to support ZENE in activities ensuring proper integration and validation of all modules of road pilot developed in WP3. UNI will be involved to support OHB-DS in activities ensuring proper integration and validation of all modules of rail pilot developed in WP3.
4.4 - Execution of the pilots and analysis of the results	DUTH	DUTH as well as Twist, ZENRS, ZENE and NELT will be involved in activities to execute testing of integrated components in relevant road environment. OHB-DS and UNI, with support of Serbian Railway Infrastructure, will be involved in activities to execute testing of integrated components in relevant rail environment.
5.1. Dissemination plan and communication activities	ZENRS	Within this Task 5.1, ALL partners will be involved throughout the project in dissemination and communication of the project's results.
5.2. Elaborate the SPATRA exploitation plan and business model	ZENRS	ALL partners will support ZENRS in performing exploitation planning and analysis to assess the prospective market uptake and production viability and market potential with EU and particularly with non-EU countries.
5.3 Engage ecosystem and increase the uptake of EU satellite-based solutions, to additional non-EU countries	ZENRS	ALL partners will support ZENRS in activities to engage ecosystem and increase the uptake of EU satellite-based solutions to additional non-EU countries (different from two non-EU project partners countries, Serbia and Ukraine)

Task Leaders will be experienced scientist and project managers and will have the following responsibilities towards the Coordinator, the WP leader, the Grant Agreement (GA).

The main responsibilities of the TLs are:

- to supply promptly to the WP Leader all information and documents to be provided to the Coordinator and the Scientific & Technical Coordinator as the Coordinator (acting on behalf of the GA) needs to fulfil obligations pursuant to the Consortium Agreement and the GA.

Innovation Manager (IM)

ZENRS will be the project's Innovation Manager and will develop and implement the project's innovation strategy. The Innovation Manager will interact with the partners engaged in techno-economic analysis as well as with the Scientific & Technical Coordinator, end-users and industry stakeholders to ensure the project's innovation and long-term sustainability. The Innovation Manager will brief all partners on the project's innovations and opportunities for exploitation on a quarterly basis and present the project's innovations results to the project's General Assembly (GA).

General Assembly (GEAS)

The GEAS will be composed of one representative from each partner organisation. The GEAS is responsible for the overall direction of the project and has power in:

- to decide upon the overall technical roadmaps of the project and work packages
- agreeing upon proposals made by the Coordinator/WP leaders for the allocation of the project budget in accordance with the Grant Agreement;
- deciding on the modalities of use, management and release of joint funds;
- agreeing upon proposals made by the Coordinator/WP leaders for (a) decisions to service notice on a defaulting partner and (b) assigning the defaulting partners tasks and budgets to other partners;
- agreeing upon proposals made by the Coordinator/WP leaders for changes to technical specifications in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement and exchange of work packages between partners, if this exchange has an effect which goes beyond the scope of the work package;
- to agree procedures and policies for the Management of knowledge;
- to approve press releases and publications by the partners with regard to the project and to avoid difficulties in the protection of potential foreground intellectual property produced in the project.

Stakeholder Board (SB)

The SPATRA Consortium will establish a Stakeholder Board, comprising a representative cross-section of stakeholders, especially including industry (road logistics, railway) members involved in the project as partners (NELT) as well those external to the project such as Serbian Railway Infrastructure (<https://infrazs.rs/>) and Transport Community (<https://www.transport-community.org/>). The Stakeholder Board will meet with partners face-to-face or electronically at least three times a year. The partners will provide a briefing on the status of the project, but most of the meeting will be devoted to a discussion with stakeholders to gather their views on the issues being addressed by the consortium and how we can leverage the project's impact.

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3.3 Project communication tools

Operating as a team with international consortium like the SPATRA Consortium is, needs a special attention when it comes to setting-up communication tools to enable smooth running of the project. Therefore, a communication infrastructure has been created to enable easy and effective communication between project partners, making extensive use of available online tooling for regular contacts, in additional to possible personal partners' contact.

There are several channels for internal communication between SPATRA partners as listed in the following:

- SPATRA document SharePoint,
- Microsoft Teams online meetings,
- People Exchange.

4. Work breakdown and schedule

The work plan of SPATRA is organized in five highly interacting, incremental, and iterative work packages (WPs), systematically developing and refining the core technology. The central three WPs (WP2-4) will design, develop, integrate and validate two EO-based applications: an EO-based drone assisted system for road traffic monitoring application and EO-based system for rail temperature prediction and assessing the risk of rail buckling due to extreme rail temperature. WP1 is dedicated to supporting project management, while WP5 will provide communication, dissemination, and exploitation. Fig. 5 below provides an overview of the work plan structure, which is broken down into five WPs with the following main purpose:

- WP1 performs the administrative and financial management of the project and coordinates the Research & Development activities of the different WPs with the help of the WP leaders.
- WP2 designs and specify requirements of the prototypes, develop the use cases and outline the architecture with APIs. Outputs of WP2 Tasks, definition of SPATRA functional and non-functional requirements (Task 2.1), specification of use-cases (Task 2.2), and specification of components and definition of integration roadmap (Task 2.3) are essential inputs to all development tasks of WP4 and to integration and validation tasks of WP4.
- WP3 develops components, algorithms and technologies, to improve monitoring and tracking of road transportation vehicles and predict rail temperature and buckling risks. In Task 3.1, a framework for data collection, harmonisation, storage, and interoperability to support all other tasks in the project will be established. SW for road pilot will be developed in Tasks 3.2 and 3.4, and the HW components for road pilot will be developed in Task 3.4. The algorithms for satellite-based rail temperature and monitoring will be developed in Tasks 3.5 and 3.6 and they will provide inputs to T3.6 as needed for development of decision-making algorithms for assessment of risks of rail buckling due to extreme temperatures. Components developed in Tasks 3.5, 3.6 and 3.7 will be all integrated in Task 3.8 in a satellite-based service for rail temperature monitoring and early risk warnings. In Task 3.9, a single-access user-oriented GUI will be developed for both pilots, for the road pilot with components developed in tasks 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4, and for the rail service integrated in Task 3.8.
- WP4 aims to pilot the created systems in a series of trials, while at the same time providing the integration and evaluation ground for all the components designed in WP2-4. In Task 4.1, specifications of scenarios for testing the solutions for both pilots developed in related tasks of WP3 will be defined. In Task 4.2 a comprehensive configuration process will be conducted to establish both SPATRA pilots, and integration and validation of all developed modules will be done in Task 4.3. Outputs of Tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3 will be inputs to Task 4.4 to assure smooth execution of both pilots and analysis of the demonstration results.
- WP5 performs dissemination and exploitation activities, and it represents a crucial element in order to ensure the impact of the project by closely engaging, from its beginning, with a diverse set of stakeholders and existing ecosystems and by implementing an effective bootstrapping and expansion strategy, relying on dissemination activities. The project results

achieved in WPs 1-4 will be disseminated and communicated in the framework of Task 5.1. SPATRA exploitation plan and business model will be developed in Task 5.2. In Task 5.3 the activities will be conducted to engage ecosystem and increase the uptake of EU satellite-based solutions to additional non-EU countries (different from two non-EU project partners countries, Serbia and Ukraine) as in line with Work Programme.

Figure 2. SPATRA PERT Diagram.

4.1 SPATRA Gantt Chart

	Leader	Structure of the work plan	year 1												year 2											
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
WP1	OHB-DS	Project management																								
T1.1	OHB-DS	Project coordination	D1.1			D1.5			D1.6			D1.7			D1.8			D1.9			D1.10			D1.11		
T1.2	OHB-DS	Scientific & Technical Coordination	D1.2/D1.4																							
T1.3	ZENRS	Innovation Management																								
T1.4	OHB-DS	Elaborate the project's DMP, ethics and regulatory strategy	D1.3																							
WP2	ZENE	Requirements and specifications																								
T2.1	OHB-DS	Define SPATRA functional and non-functional requirements																								
T2.2	ZENE	Develop use case specification																								
T2.3	UNI	Devise a component specification and integration roadmap	D2.1																							
WP3	OHB-DS	Development of SPATRA algorithms and technology																								
T3.1	OHB-DS	Data collection, harmonisation, storage, and interoperability API													D3.1											
T3.2	ZENRS	Copernicus Sentinel-2 truck detection													D3.2											
T3.3	DUTH	Machine learning / Image vision for Drone													D3.2											
T3.4	ZENE	In-truck EGNSS trackers													D3.2											
T3.5	OHB-DS	Rail environment temperature profile based on satellite data																								
T3.6	OHB-DS	Rail track temperature prediction model																								
T3.7	UNI	Algorithm for assessment of rail track buckling risk																								
T3.8	OHB-DS	Implementation of space-based service for monitoring of rail temperature and early warnings																								
T3.9	OHB-DS	GUI Dashboard													D3.3											
WP4	UNI	Validation: Use-cases																								
T4.1	NELT	Specification of the use cases for testing and validation methodology																								
T4.2	UNI	Configure and establish SPATRA pilots													D4.1											
T4.3	ZENE	Integration and validation of modules													D4.2											
T4.4	DUTH	Execution of the pilots and analysis of the results													D4.3											
WP5	ZENE	Dissemination, communication and exploitation																								
T5.1	ZENRS	Dissemination plan and communication activities	D5.1																							
T5.2	ZENRS	Elaborate the SPATRA exploitation plan and business model	D5.2																							
T5.3	ZENRS	Engage ecosystem and increase the uptake of EU satellite-based solutions, to additional non-EU countries																								
MS1		Project kick-off and coordination plan approved	◆																							
MS2		Data DMP and regulatory strategy finalized and approved	◆																							
MS3		Requirements and specifications finalized and approved	◆																							
MS4		Data recorded for training/developing models of both pilots	◆																							
MS5		Development of satellite-/drone vision-based technologies for road pilot completed	◆																							
MS6		Development of satellite-/machine learning -based technologies for rail pilot completed	◆																							
MS7		Use case specifications and validation methodology approved	◆																							
MS8		Integration and validation of SPATRA modules completed	◆																							
MS9		Dissemination plan and communication activities initiated	◆																							
MS10		SPATRA exploitation plan and business model elaborated and approved	◆																							

Figure 3. SPATRA Gantt Chart with detailed project time planning

4.2 SPATRA Deliverables

The following table shows the deliverables within SPATRA with the associated Lead Beneficiaries.

Table 3. SPATRA Deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	WP No.	Short name of lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery date (in months)	Project internal reviewers
D1.1	Project Management Plan (PMP)	1	OHB-DS	R	PU	M2	ZENRS, UNI
D1.2	Risk management and project quality plan	1	OHB-DS	R	PU	M3	ZENE
D1.3	Data Management Plan	1	OHB-DS	DMP	SEN	M5	ZENRS, UNI
D1.4	Quarterly Report 1	1	OHB-DS	R	SEN	M3	ALL
D1.5	Quarterly Report 2	1	OHB-DS	R	SEN	M6	ALL
D1.6	Quarterly Report 3	1	OHB-DS	R	SEN	M9	ALL
D1.7	Quarterly Report 4	1	OHB-DS	R	SEN	M12	ALL
D1.8	Quarterly Report 5	1	OHB-DS	R	SEN	M15	ALL
D1.9	Quarterly Report 6	1	OHB-DS	R	SEN	M18	ALL
D1.10	Quarterly Report 7	1	OHB-DS	R	SEN	M21	ALL
D1.11	Quarterly Report 8	1	OHB-DS	R	SEN	M24	ALL
D2.1	Requirements and use cases specifications	2	UNI	R	PU	M6	NELT, OHB-DS
D3.1	Data collection and harmonisation process	3	ZENE	R	PU	M14	OHB-DS, UNI

	documentation						
D3.2	Report on SPATRA technology development for road transport use case	3	DUTH	DEM	SEN	M20	UNI, ZENE
D3.3	Report on SPATRA technology development for rail transport use case	3	OHB-DS	DEM	SEN	M20	Twist, ZENE
D4.1	Pilot Plan and Protocol Specification:	4	Nelt	R	PU	M9	UNI, ZENRS
D4.2	Integration and Validation Report	4	ZENE	R	PU	M22	OHB-DS, UNI
D4.3	Pilot Results and Analysis Report	4	UNI	R	PU	M24	OHB-DS, ZENE
D5.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan	5	OHB-DS	R	PU	M3	ZENRS
D5.2	SPATRA exploitation plan	5	ZENRS	R	SEN	M24	OHB-DS, UNI

4.3 SPATRA Milestones and review meetings

The details about project Milestones are given in Table below.

Table 4. SPATRA Milestones

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related work package(s)	Due date (in month)	Means of verification
MS1	Project kick-off and coordination plan approved	WP1	M2	D1.1 approved
MS2	Data DMP and regulatory strategy finalized and approved	WP1	M5	D1.3 approved
MS3	Requirements and specifications	WP2	M6	D2.1 approved

	finalized and approved			
MS4	Data recorded for training/developing models of both pilots	WP3	M14	D3.1 approved
MS5	Development of satellite-/drone vision-based technologies for road pilot completed	WP3	M20	D3.2 approved
MS6	Development of satellite-/machine learning -based technologies for rail pilot completed	WP3	M20	D3.3 approved
MS7	Use case specifications and validation methodology approved	WP4	M9	D4.1 approved- SPATRA pilots configured and established
MS8	Integration and validation of SPATRA modules completed	WP4	M22	D4.2 approved
MS9	Dissemination plan and communication activities initiated	WP5	M3	D5.1 approved
MS10	SPATRA exploitation plan and business model elaborated and approved	WP5	M24	D5.2 approved

In accordance with the reporting periods agreed in the Grant Agreement, RP1: from Month 1 to month 12 and RP2: from Month 13 to Month 24, there will be two review meetings as given the Table below.

Table 5. Project reviews

Review No.	Review name	Timing (in month)
RV1	Interim review	M13
RV2	Final review	M24

As according to the Grant Agreement at the end of each reporting period periodic reports consisting of technical and financial periodic reports shall be prepared by the Consortium and submit to funding organisation EC/EUSPA for the review and final approval.